

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Kinkoumana**FIRST NAME:** Ibrahim**PROGRAM CODE:** DME**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)
The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Course Management Systems (CMS)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have always dreamed of pursuing my doctorate in English to be bilingual. Through my online research, I came across a famous university known for providing sustained knowledge. I am so grateful to be enrolled in EUCLID University's Doctor of Philosophy program in Monitoring, Measurement, and Evaluation. The EUCLID University is an international organization that is part of the United Nations treaty and provides online courses for professionals and students all over the world. As a resident of Mali, where English is a second language, EUCLID University has been essential in helping me pursue my doctoral studies without interrupting my professional commitments while improving my proficiency in English. Since I was accepted to this university, I undertook extensive measures to enhance my linguistic and academic competencies. This included immersing myself in intensive online language training at the Linguistic Pilot Centre of Yaoundé, Cameroon, supplemented by immersive experiences in Ghana during the years 2018 and 2023. This prestigious university provided me with supplementary resources and tools that enriched my academic journey. I have learned a lot from videos on software such as Grammarly and Zotero, as well as the course pack material for period one.

In this response paper; I would like to discuss my understanding of the course pack, which is structured into eight parts: essay writing, punctuation, American vs. British English, plagiarism, style guide, Course Management System (CMS), and sample correction to papers. My work will deal with essay writing,

2) ESSAY WRITING

This section aims to provide a general overview of the basics of essay writing. I noticed that academic writing requires confirming or contesting hypotheses based on evidence. This course provides steps to consider before starting an essay. Firstly, it is important to define the research questions and give a draft of an initial plan as early as possible. A good essay plan can guide research and help answer questions. Secondly, research on the topic can be done by reading extensively and taking notes. I understood that reading requires many skills like creativity and critical thinking. I also have to structure ideas while reading by following the introduction, body, and conclusion format. In the introduction, I should introduce the topic from the general to the specific, providing orientation and a road map for the writing. In the body, I should discuss the topic with arguments and pieces of evidence for the answers to the research questions. In the conclusion, the essay must be concluded from the specific to the general. There, the research questions are restated, the main points are summarized, and a new idea is introduced. Lastly, I have to avoid plagiarism by referencing the material while editing the essay. EUCLID University recommends the Turabian style for references (author's name, date) or (author's name, date, pages) (EUCLID 2021, 7-12). When editing my essay, I should pay attention to its structure, the logical sequence of the main ideas, and the use of logical connectors. This first material advises me to think critically, avoid building long sentences, avoid using the same expression repeatedly, and avoid plagiarism.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

I have learned that punctuation is vital in reducing the length of sentences and making their meaning clear. Although some punctuations have similar functions in different sentences, many of them can have varying meanings depending on the context. Most punctuations have the same usage in both US and UK English and in other languages as well (EUCLID 2021, 15-23). They are especially helpful in short sentences as they aid in making our writing more comprehensible to readers. Additionally, I have also discovered that some punctuation is more suitable for poetry than academic writing.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Progress in many fields, such as technology, media, culture, and sciences, has contributed to the spread of US English all over the world since World War II. UK English is mostly spoken as a colonial language in many African English-speaking countries. I

noticed that differences exist in pronunciation, spelling, meaning, and vocabulary (EUCLID 2021, 24-32).

The most common observations are different pronunciations and the same spelling or the same pronunciation and different spelling. Then, having the same word or term with similar spelling and pronunciation or additional meanings could be possible. In terms of grammar, syntax, and punctuation, the difference comes in the use of date writing, commas, and periods, as well as some honorific words. In some sentences with collective name, the verb must be in the plural in UK English. In the same country, the use of some words can change, as is the case in the US between the native Americans and the Black Americans or the Indian descendants.

5) PLAGIARISM

In academic writing, plagiarism is using information, whether it's words or ideas, without properly citing the source (EUCLID 2021, 33). I have learned that giving our response paper to be completed by someone else is also considered plagiarism. The best way to avoid plagiarism is to properly cite the authors and sources of information. From this material, I have learned that there are two types of citations: in-text citations and a list of works cited. When using borrowed statistics, data, or any other kind of information, it is important to use round brackets with the author's name and the date of publication, for instance (Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck & Dr. Kabiru Gulma, 2021). Quotations should only be used when reciting the author's exact words and should be limited to make it look like our own research. Paraphrasing can help summarize the author's ideas in our own words to avoid excessive use of quotations. However, there are certain cases where citing the author is not necessary, such as when referring to common knowledge or repeated information. On the other hand, the list of works cited, which includes the bibliography or references, must be given at the end of the writing. The rules for referencing differ depending on the type of information being used. For books, the general rule is "Kabiru Gulma. 2021. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University." For footnotes, the rule is "Kabiru Gulma. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1" (EUCLID 2021, 39).

6) COURSE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

I noticed that when more than two spelling or forms of plural are given, the first one listed must be prioritized. For abbreviations words, only well-known words and traditional honorific words can be used in the writing paper. As known from primary school, a sentence always starts with a capital letter and finishes with a full stop. But some words like geographical names and ethnical groups stand in as capital letters at the beginning. Furthermore, compound words are used in their various forms and different meanings. The most common use of italics is when we emphasize something. I knew from this course that if a sentence starts with a number, it must be written out. It can remain in numeral number when it concerns a measurement.

7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the structured examination of essay writing fundamentals, punctuations, nuances between American and British English, strategies for mitigating plagiarism, and adherence to style guides such as CMS have engendered a deeper appreciation of the material. These insights and a commitment to academic integrity and rigor highlight the foundational principles supporting my scholarly pursuit.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.